

Street Survey on Societal Acceptance of Blue Carbon along the German Coasts 2022 - sea4soCiety Study Report

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As part of the project: Searching for solutions for Carbon-sequestration in coastal ecosystems (sea4soCiety): Innovative Approaches to Enhancing the Carbon Storage Potential of Coastal Vegetated Ecosystems, financed by the Federal German Ministry for Research and Education (03F0896F)

June 2024

Abstract

In the context of climate change mitigation, ‘carbon dioxide removal’ (CDR) refers to the capture and long-term storage of atmospheric CO₂. ‘Blue carbon’ is a nature-based marine CDR option as it refers to carbon trapped in marine environments. Coastal vegetated ecosystems (CVEs) are assumed to have huge potentials as carbon sinks. Within the sea4soCieTy consortium as part of the interdisciplinary CDRmare research mission (Phase I, 2021 – 2024), we conducted a survey along the German coasts to gather values and perceptions of coastal residents regarding their home region, CVEs and climate change. This publication contains a study report on the metadata of the survey (research context, data generation and processing) and the original questionnaire (in German).

Information on the study and the research context

This study report presents the documentation of a street survey. Structure and content are inspired by a guideline for reporting qualitative research data (Heuer et al., 2020). The purpose of this survey was to investigate the potential of blue carbon strategies along the German coasts from a societal perspective. It unfolds in the context of climate change perception and societal acceptance of local interventions to promote coastal vegetated ecosystems as carbon sinks. The survey was conducted in 2022 along the coasts of Schleswig-Holstein and Lower Saxony. The underlying research was integrated in the research consortium “Searching for solutions for Carbon-sequestration in coastal ecosystems” (sea4soCieTy). The consortium is part of the German Marine Research Alliance (Deutsche Allianz Meeresforschung, DAM) research mission “CDRmare”, financed by the Federal German Ministry for Research and Education (2021-2024). The study is based at the Department of Geography of the University of Hamburg, in the working group of Prof. Dr. Beate Ratter.

At the 21st Conference of the Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, in Paris in 2015, the global community agreed on limiting global warming to 2°C, preferably 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels. In light of this so called ‘Paris Agreement’, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) developed recommendations to stay within the agreed 1.5 to 2°C range. These pathways imply net zero emissions by mid-century, and the reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions is key. Yet, reduction alone will not suffice. In addition, the utilization of ‘negative emissions’ or ‘carbon dioxide removal’ (CDR) is needed to offset hard-to-abate emissions. CDR corresponds to the capture and long-term storage of atmospheric CO₂ (IPCC, 2018).

‘Blue carbon’ is a nature-based marine CDR option as it refers to atmospheric carbon trapped in the oceans and coastal shelf seas. Coastal vegetated ecosystems (CVEs) such as mangroves, macroalgae, seagrass meadows or salt marshes capture more than half the CO₂ the oceans sequester. Their carbon burial rates per size are roughly 30 to 50 times higher than land-based forests (McLeod et al. 2011) Hence, CVEs could play a critical role in blue carbon and CDR. Besides carbon sequestration, these coastal vegetated ecosystems are known for ecosystem services and functions such as coastal protection and biodiversity.

The conservation and expansion of these ecosystems for the purpose of enhancing carbon sequestration is considered a socio-ecological interaction. The overarching goals of the project, in which the survey was conducted, are

- to understand different coastal cultures and social framings of the coast,
- to identify potential synergies and trade-offs of blue carbon interventions,
- to analyse social, cultural, economic, legal, and political feasibilities,
- to activate local knowledge and innovation, and
- to take power relations and governance systems into account for the identification of early triggers for social resistance and acceptance by change agents, stakeholders, and residents.

The results can form the basis for designing deliberative governance strategies. The aim of the coastal population street survey was to identify certain values and knowledges of the coastal population in Germany that might be affected by future blue carbon measures.

Data generation: preparation and implementation

This study consists of a two-part population survey based on a questionnaire. It was conducted as a random street survey in open public spaces along the German coasts. In March 2022, 132 local residents were interviewed on both coasts of Schleswig-Holstein, and in July 2022, 90 people participated in the same survey on the coast of Lower Saxony. The interviewees voluntarily gave their prior informed consent. The questionnaire included 10 open-ended and 40 closed questions and was structured into four chapters: place attachment and environment, regional climate change, political participation, and sociodemographic data (The German-language questionnaire is attached). For the closed questions, the respondents were presented with a Likert scale with options to agree or disagree with given statements using five predefined answers: “yes,” “rather yes,” “rather no,” “no,” or “do not know.” For each trip, four students were coached, and together with the corresponding author, the mixed-gender group conducted one-on-one surveys. Coaching, taking notes of verbal reactions and non-verbal expressions, and holding reflection sessions twice daily supported the comparability of the survey results independent of the interviewer and interpretations of presented answers. Interviews were conducted through the use of tablets. The questionnaire was fed into Kobotoolbox, a free survey software, including free fields for the open questions and remarks by the interviewers. Data is handled in accordance with a detailed data management plan developed by CDRmare (Placke & Mehrtens, 2022), which was adapted for the sea4soCieTy consortium and approved by the DAM.

Twelve survey locations were chosen to represent the rural and urban coastal populations of Schleswig-Holstein and Lower Saxony as well as the North Sea and Baltic Sea. Places were selected according to size and infrastructure (more than 1,000 inhabitants and busy public spaces) and represent different administrative districts. Surveys were mainly conducted on the street, in public places, in pedestrian zones, and in front of supermarkets. At each selected location, 11–24 interviews were conducted. The survey locations (place and district) were:

- North Sea coast of Schleswig-Holstein: Büsum, Dittmarschen; Husum, Nordfriesland; Bredstedt, Nordfriesland
- Baltic Sea coast of Schleswig-Holstein: Eckernförde, Rendsburg-Eckernförde; Kiel, Kiel; Schönberg, Plön; Neustadt, Ostholstein
- North Sea coast of Lower Saxony: Emden, Emden; Greetsiel, Aurich; Wilhelmshaven, Wilhelmshaven; Varel, Friesland; Cuxhaven, Cuxhaven

Processing, analysing and potential reuse of the data

All answers provided were directly inserted into the Kobotoolbox software. Data were downloaded into an Excel sheet. The Excel sheet was checked for technical correctness. Three interviews were cancelled and not included in the analysis. Most of the remaining 222 participants answered all questions, so the sample size is generally between 218 and 222. A question about the place of residence was to be answered with the respective postal code, and an analysis was carried out regarding residency. This information was used to apply a rurality index (Küpper, 2016) to give each place of origin a rurality value based on several indices, such as the density of settlements and the proportion of agriculture and forestry in a municipality or the distance to large centres. Spearman’s correlation coefficients between closed questions were calculated with SPSS.

The participants were between 16 and 88 years of age. Compared to the population of the federal states of Schleswig-Holstein and Lower Saxony, most of the age groups in the survey differed <20% from state averages. Only the 16–25-year-old age group was overrepresented by almost 50%, while the 36–45-year-old age group was underrepresented by 40%. The mean age was 49 years, and 52% of the participants were female, reflecting the states’ populations in mean age and gender.

The data was prepared for an internal project report (Fink & Ratter, 2023) and parts of the data set were used for an empirical open-access paper (Fink & Ratter, 2024). Within the “sea4soCieTy” project, the questionnaire and study design were translated and modified for application in an Indonesian context. Further reuses within the sea4soCieTy context to cover additional regions or generate long-term data are not specifically planned, but potentially possible.

References

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About sea4soCiety

sea4soCiety

Searching for solutions for Carbon-sequestration in coastal ecosystems

sea4soCiety aims at developing innovative and societally accepted approaches to better utilise the natural potential for carbon storage in vegetation-rich coastal ecosystems. sea4soCiety is one of a total of six research consortia in the research mission “Marine carbon sinks in decarbonization pathways” of the German Marine Research Alliance (DAM), funded by BMBF. sea4soCiety will determine the quantity and quality of the "blue carbon" stores in four different types of coastal ecosystems on the German North Sea and Baltic Sea coasts, in the Caribbean and the Malaysian coast.

The working group “Socio-cultural Framing & Deliberative Coastal Management” is a sub-project of sea4soCiety and conducts qualitative research on societal acceptance and the interrelationships of blue carbon storage in terms of co-benefits, risks, governance and economic valorisation potential.